

Journal: Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering

DOI: 10.3233/ICA-200637

Human-Robot Interaction in Industry 4.0 based on an Internet of Things Real-Time Gesture Control System

Luis Roda-Sanchez ^a, Teresa Olivares ^{a,b}, Celia Garrido-Hidalgo ^a, José Luis de la Vara ^{a,b} and Antonio Fernández-Caballero ^{a,b}

^a *Instituto de Investigación en Informática de Albacete (I3A), 02071-Albacete, Spain*

^b *Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Departamento de Sistemas Informáticos, 02071-Albacete, Spain*
E-mail: {Luis.Roda, Teresa.Olivares, Celia.Garrido, JoseLuis.delaVara, Antonio.Fdez}@uclm.es

Abstract

In the context of fast-growing digitization of industrial environments, Industry 4.0 aims to improve key elements to achieve more efficient processes, flexibility in customizing products and reduction in energy consumption, among other objectives. This paper presents a system that exploits the Internet of Things (IoT), massive data computation, and human-robot collaboration to reach these goals. The described system combines technological and human-centered aspects to enhance human-robot interaction. In fact, the human factor cannot be left aside when technological advances affecting society are foreseen. The proposal has been tested on a gesture control system that enables a natural interaction with a robotic arm through the use of IoT-oriented inertial measurement unit devices. These devices capture the movements of both human's arms. Experiments of a technical nature have been run to measure accuracy and latency. In addition, human-centered tests have been conducted with real users to determine the level of intuitiveness and acceptance of the proposed gesture control. The results obtained demonstrate that the proposal meets the demands in terms of real-time, success rate, flexibility and scalability, which are fundamental requirements in Industry 4.0. The usability results have enabled drawing useful conclusions on the use of such human-robot interaction systems.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Industry 4.0, Gesture control, Human-robot interaction, Wireless communications, Wearables.

1. Introduction

A consequence of the advent of Industry 4.0 is that many industrial tasks will be undertaken by robots or in collaboration with them. In the near future, robots will play a fundamental role in industrial routine tasks, such as movement of heavy or dangerous materials, exposure to hazardous environments and high precision operations. Unfortunately, since many workers are not prepared to operate modern industrial robots, given their associated increased complexity, Industry 4.0 may lead to social vulnerability and culminate into the rejection of valuable technology. Therefore, natural human-robot interaction (HRI) systems focused on industrial scenarios enabled by heterogeneous Internet of Things (IoT) applications [1] must become a prior-

ity when developing industrial solutions. Even the concept of the Internet of Robotic Things is already being introduced [2]. This is the case of smart gesture control systems based on cost-effective devices to perform natural HRI.

There is a growing trend in the contribution of IoT to industry [3,4]. In addition, there are many compelling works in HRI based on gesture recognition, be it in the industry [5,6,7,8,9,10], with a general purpose [11,12,13,14], at smart homes [15], for real time applications [16,17], hand detection [18,19] or healthcare [20]. Although HRI is important in essence, the manner in which the interaction is performed is equally crucial. Outstanding aspects such as a natural interaction, and an easier and faster development process are

suitably addressed by researchers who attempt to improve HRI (e.g. [21,22,2]).

In this regards, our research team has already developed two algorithms oriented to movement recognition and heart rate measurement. The objective was to digitize industrial facilities focused on power-aware algorithms to enhance working conditions [23]. In addition, a smart factory scenario that leverages several wireless communication technologies and wearables has been recently proposed [24]. These are transparent to workers for the purpose of avoiding social disruption, thus satisfying a major challenge of the Industry 4.0. Also regarding IoT and robots, agent-oriented software engineering enables modeling behaviors and communications (e.g. [25,26]) and data fusion and machine learning enhances data analysis and decision making (e.g. [27]).

Many studies have focused on HRI and gesture recognition through a variety of technologies. Considering the type of sensor, firstly there are systems based on color (RGB) and depth (D) cameras. There are studies that obtain excellent recognition results using RGB cameras [28,29]. Some works have directly tackled HRI by means of RGB cameras [16,17,30]. Depth cameras have also faced HRI [31,32,33,34,35]. Specifically, for hand detection and continuous control of robots, i.e. accurately tracking movements performed by the user, depth cameras embedded in commercial devices like Leap Motion are being used [36]. Other works use both RGB and depth sensors (RGB-D) to achieve a higher accuracy in 3D recognition [37, 38,39,40]. The commercial device based on RGB-D most used in people detection is the Microsoft Kinect. Lastly, inertial measurement units (IMUs) have also been proposed for robust HRI [6,14,41].

Obviously, each technology introduced above offers different characteristics and is intended to be used for specific purposes. Depending on the task at hand, the most appropriate device should be selected. Solutions based on RGB cameras entail the traditional problems of 2D computer vision. Concretely, 3D movement detection, a complex task in computer vision, which needs machine learning algorithms, is a severe drawback for gesture control in HRI. Although Leap Motion is highly accurate in controlling the position and movements of the hands, the user is limited to operate very close to the device. The Kinect provides body skeleton detection and is suitable for pose estimation and movement recognition affecting the entire body. Therefore, its design was not originally intended to directly manage the movements of a robot.

On the other hand, IMUs are adequate for 3D movement recognition, provide freedom of user location, demand low hardware requirements and are ideal in the Internet of Robotic Things. Hence, the system presented in this paper introduces a real-time HRI system based on IMUs that meets the essential requirements of IoT for the Industry 4.0. The system meets the real-time requirements of industrial environments, accuracy, flexibility to learn new movements rapidly and a natural interaction that allows the worker to adapt as quickly as possible to the process.

This paper extends a very recent article [42] and is the result of our multidisciplinary experience [43,44, 45] in different fields including sensors, wireless networks and HRI. The remainder of the paper is as follows. Section 2 presents a general description of the gesture control system, while Section 3 provides a detailed explanation of the implementation. The experimentation is described in Section 4. Section 5 includes the results and the analysis of technical and human-centered tests. Lastly, our main conclusions are outlined in Section 6.

2. General Description of the Gesture Control System

This section describes the overall operation and the principal ideas underlying the conducted research. Figure 1 shows a state machine with the different conditions considered in the system. The figure facilitates the comprehension of the explanations offered below.

The main hardware components of the system are two wearables developed in our research team, which are a wristband to control the system's modes and another to perform the movements that define the robot's tasks; a processing board; and a robot used to conduct the experiments. The system starts at an *Inactive* (1) state to avoid hazardous situations. It stands in this state until a command is sent from the wearable denominated *ControlaBLE*. This control wearable supplies five possible commands calculated from an accelerometer after a human operator realizes one of five intuitive hand positions (control disabled; low velocity; medium velocity; high velocity; emergency), as depicted in Table 1.

The entire operation of the system is determined by this control device, since no further processing occurs until the operator selects a valid mode via *ControlaBLE*. When the operator triggers the *Active* (2) state, the robot can be handled with three different velocities

Figure 1. State machine of the proposed system [42].

in order to tune the precision required for each task. Among the five control possibilities, any of the three speed modes (low, medium and high velocity) transits the system to the *Active* (2) state.

Furthermore, there are two additional commands to disable movement-processing on the robot, which enables a more natural interaction. The *Inactive* (1) state can be established from any *ControlaBLE* state except the *Home* (3) one. This is a special condition produced due to an emergency stop. It has been added to issue a fast manner to place the robot in a fail-safe position in case of alarm, which is compulsory in any industrial system. The emergency command is endowed with the highest priority, which provides a prompt action independently from the actual system's state.

Our proposal is not intended to provide continuous monitoring, as it might be the case using computer vision, where tasks must be performed at a slow speed to achieve an adequate accuracy. In this case, the idea is to provide the robot with skills, i.e. different types of actions. By using the wristband called *OperaBLE*, movements that correspond to the different skills of the robot are performed. In this manner, a benefit is obtained regarding the execution time of the tasks, since

they can be accomplished at the speed of a conventional industrial robot. *OperaBLE* enables switching among different robot movements. In this case, Table 2 shows the five movements defined so far in a first experimental design with a robotic arm (forward; backward; right; left; pick/drop). *OperaBLE* transmits raw movement data, while *ControlaBLE* performs a different preprocessing and sends a command directly to the processing device. Once the mode selected by *ControlaBLE* reaches the *Active* (2) state, five predefined movements are ready to trigger different commands. Nonetheless, notice that our low-frequency movement characterization algorithm (*LoMoCA*) [23] is prepared to recognize more movements in the future.

LoMoCA is based on dynamic time warping (DTW) and has been specifically designed to work at extremely low sampling frequencies. Our algorithm achieves movement recognition under sample rates around 10 Hz, which is 10 times lower than most previous approaches [14,46,47,10]. Actually, according to the literature, the response time should be lower than 100 ms to contemplate real-time control in tasks involving human control in terms of industrial requirements [48,49,50]. Consequently, *LoMoCA* pro-

Table 1

ControlaBLE: positions and associated control commands.

Control disabled	Low velocity	Medium velocity	High velocity	Emergency

Table 2

OperaBLE: defined movements and associated actions.

Forward	Backward	Left	Right	Pick/Drop

vides advantages such as the increase of fluency and the reduction of power consumption. In addition, *LoMoCA* can be built on lightweight devices, with its low-processing requirements being the key towards scalable networks that enable the coexistence of more connected wearables. Although *LoMoCA* was already presented, thanks to the changes addressed (see Section 3.3), the algorithm has evolved to enhance accuracy and is currently capable of meeting industrial real-time requirements. As the structure and main stages of the algorithm remain unchanged, it was determined to keep the same name.

Additionally, Table 2 shows the axes involved for each movement, the corresponding path and the command activated in each case. The *Movement Processing* (4) state is only triggered when the *OperaBLE*'s movement is significant enough. When the data received match a pattern that has been previously recorded in the processing board, the corresponding command is transmitted to the robot controller represented as *Movement* (5) state. Finally, after the movement of the robot, the current position of the robot is sent back to enable further processing.

3. Implementation of the Gesture Control System

This section introduces the materials, resources and architecture deployed. It is split into four parts, namely

the proposed architecture, the materials and resources used, the description of the movement recognition algorithm, and the system's properties. The objective is to provide a comprehensive description and to shed light on the existing conditions of the work.

3.1. System Architecture

The architecture of the complete system is depicted in Figure 2. It is divided in different layers with several stages and functions. In first place, as part of sensor and control layers, there are two intelligent wearables (*OperaBLE* and *ControlaBLE*) using the same hardware configuration. In this case, the data acquisition stage, which is used to obtain acceleration and angular velocity, is based on a microcontroller board with Bluetooth low energy (BLE) connectivity and an IMU. The cover was fabricated with a 3D printer [51].

The processing layer connected to the wearables is implemented on a single board computer (SBC). The board is responsible for managing the data supplied by both wearables and transmitted via BLE. There is a master-slave connection between the wearables and the SBC, being the latter the master. When an active command is sent from *ControlaBLE* (any velocity), the movement is processed by *LoMoCA* algorithm through several stages (detailed in Section 3.3).

The communication management is a fundamental aspect enabling the processing of different users

Figure 2. System architecture: layers, stages, functions and communications.

in isolation and simultaneously. Once the movement has been recognized, the matching command is routed to the robot controller board remotely via Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT). In addition, the processing device integrates an MQTT broker in order to define a set of topics and manage connections to establish remote communication. For this purpose, three topics are created in the broker where the MQTT publisher can send commands: robot movement, robot controller, and emergency. Some priorities have been set up, starting from the low-priority topic that sends movement-related commands performed by *OperaBLE*. The robot controller topic shares information about control commands coming from *ControlaBLE*. Finally, the highest-priority topic is the so-called emergency, where alarm commands are published. Besides, the data exchange is bi-directional to get feedback information from the robot such as its current position.

The last part of the system is attached to the robot. It includes a Raspberry Pi 2, a controller board managing six servos via pulse width modulation, and the robotic arm structure that performs the action defined by the operator at each moment. The subscriber MQTT is programmed at the SBC of the processing layer, where the subscription to topics takes place.

3.2. Hardware and Software

With regard to the specific materials and resources used at each layer, a summary of the hardware and

software elements used is presented in Table 3. As highlighted, all the components are low-power and low-cost, which has been considered convenient. In fact, considering that the requirements are met using these devices, a baseline can be established from which it is only possible to achieve better performance by replacing these devices with others that have a higher power consumption. On the software side, the system has also been designed to be easily scaled up and to keep the fluidity required for a proper operation.

The second column of Table 3 shows the hardware components at each layer of the system. The software components and main libraries are indicated in the third column and, finally, the communication protocols are specified.

Both wearables are composed of the same hardware elements, although each one executes a different program. The basic components are microcontroller, accelerometer, gyroscope, and battery. In addition, the communication protocols are indicated in last column in order to highlight the heterogeneity of the system.

Regarding the software and main libraries, the programming language selected for development and deployment is JavaScript. It is used in the Node.js environment, which is a relevant factor for the system's throughput. Node.js is an open source server environment oriented to events that uses JavaScript as programming language. Asynchronous programming permits an improved efficiency and a high processing velocity, since it can perform several tasks in parallel.

Table 3
Summary of hardware and software elements.

Layer	Hardware	Software	Communication
Sensor	LSM303 (x2)	-	I ² C
	L3GD20H (x2)		
Control	LightBlue Bean (x2)	Fusion 360 ²	I ² C
	105 mAh battery (x2)	Arduino IDE ²	BLE
Processing	BLE CSR 4.0	Noble ³	BLE
	RPi 2 model B ¹	Node.js ²	MQTT
		MQTT-Mosca ³	
Network	RPi 2 model B ¹	Node.js ²	MQTT
Processing	RPi 2 model B	Node.js ²	MQTT
			I ² C
Control	PWM/Servo HAT	Johnny-five ³	I ² C
			PWM
Actuator	Robot structure	-	PWM
	MG996R Servo (x6)		

¹ Shared hardware; ² Software components; ³ Main libraries

Furthermore, Node.js provides high scalability and the proper management enables many simultaneous connections.

Moreover, several communication protocols are used to deploy the system. This is the case of I²C for wired connections, BLE for transmitting data from intelligent wearables to the processing board, and MQTT to achieve remote communications between the processing node and the robot controller. MQTT follows a client/server communication scheme, where the server is usually known as broker. It is a lightweight machine-to-machine protocol that uses a publish-subscribe method based on the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). It is suitable for constrained systems with high accuracy requirements and it is up to 90 times faster than Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) messaging [52].

3.3. Description of the Movement Recognition Algorithm

Gesture recognition has been studied for years, usually through computer vision. This approach is normally quite accurate. However, (1) it consumes many resources, (2) it is invasive and thus can generate rejection and privacy problems due to the need to be recorded, (3) it is usually located in a fixed position or difficult to move, and, although efforts are being made in this regard, (4) it often requires significant processing time. This encouraged us to develop a gesture control system from another viewpoint with the aim of achieving a non-invasive device, capable of recognizing movements through motion sensors with a minimum consumption of resources and energy.

With this aim, preprocessing is made on the wearables in order to send only useful data to the processing device. In fact, this is one of the most critical points in terms of battery consumption. A summary of the *OperaBLE*'s operating mode performed to minimize consumption is shown in Algorithm 1, where only the relevant movements are considered and the device remains in a deep sleep mode until an acceleration interruption occurs.

Algorithm 1 Preprocessing in OperaBLE.

```

1: procedure PREPROCESSING
2:   if Relevant movement then
3:     Data source check
4:     Movement vectors ← Movement Data
5:   else
6:     Active accelerometer interruptions
7:     Deep Sleep mode
8:   if End of movement then
9:     Encode Movement vectors
10:    Send Movement vectors

```

The idea behind the implementation on the processing side is the achievement of real-time gesture recognition. To this end, the *LoMoCA* algorithm has been developed, enabling the characterization of movements using a low-sampling frequency. Using fewer samples per movement reduces the recognition time, but it increases the complexity of the algorithm itself to achieve a high success rate. To this purpose, the number of axes involved in the recognition process has been increased, using both a three-axis accelerometer and a three-axis gyroscope.

The movement recognition procedure is shown in Algorithm 2, where some abbreviations have been used in order to facilitate the representation of the pseudo-code. The meaning of the abbreviations used in Algorithm 2, equation (1), and equation (2) is the following one:

- Acc_{Diff} is the *acceleration difference*
- A_M is the *movement axis*
- A_{M-N} is the *normalized movement axis*
- A_P is the *pattern axis*
- A_{P-N} is the *normalized pattern axis*
- C_S is the *ControlaBLE state*
- DF is the *differential factor*
- DF_{RA} is the *differential factor of relevant axes*
- DF_T is the *sum of differential factors*
- DL is the *dynamic limit*
- DL_M is the *dynamic limit of movement*

- DL_P is the dynamic limit of pattern
- N_{RA} is the number of relevant axes
- S_M is the number of movement samples
- S_P is the number of pattern samples

The processing begins with the reception of the movement vectors. An analysis of these data is performed to determine the degrees of freedom (DOF) selected, apply the proper decoding method, and adjust the subsequent processing. This is necessary because the system allows the gyroscope to be deactivated to save energy when extra precision is not required, using only data from the accelerometer. After the DOF adjustment, i.e. three DOF when only the accelerometer is active and six DOF when the gyroscope data is also added, *LoMoCA* starts with the selection of a pattern stored in the processing board and then an axis within this pattern. The system does not have a training and testing period because it is based on the accurate comparison between the movement performed and the movement patterns stored previously.

The normalization stage plays a fundamental role, since it makes possible a first classification of the movement performed in a rapid manner. The normalization equation (1) shows the procedure followed with each axis. When the selected axis of the pattern is normalized, the same normalization process is checked in the movement axis. If it is also normalized because the variation between the minimum and maximum value is sufficient, the next axis is checked. On the contrary, if the pattern axis is not normalized, the current movement is evaluated and the system should obtain the same result. In case the movement axis were normalized, the algorithm would consider different movements and would continue the comparison with the next pattern stored. On the basis of these considerations, in order to continue with the processing, the normalized axes in the pattern movement and the movement performed must match to consider that pattern in the next stage.

$$A_M(x) = \frac{x \in A_M}{\max(|x|) \in A_M} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

In the following stages only the relevant axes, i.e. the normalized axes, are considered, which reduces the processing time. The next step is the dynamic limit calculation (detailed in equation 2), which is based on the number of samples of the movements being compared. Therefore, the threshold is determined for each movement-pattern comparison.

Algorithm 2 Movement recognition procedure.

```

1: procedure PROCESSING
2:   if  $C_S \neq \text{Emergency}$  and  $C_S \neq \text{Stop}$  then
3:     Movement vectors reception
4:     Data analysis and DOF adjustment
5:   LoMoCA:
6:     Pattern selection
7:     Axis selection
8:   Normalization:
9:     if  $A_{P-N}$  then
10:      if  $Acc_{Diff}$  of  $A_{M-N} > 4m/s^2$  then
11:         $A_{M-N} \leftarrow$  axis normalization
12:         $A_P$  and  $A_M$  relevant
13:      else
14:        Different movements
15:        goto LoMoCA
16:      else
17:        if  $Acc_{Diff}$  of  $A_{M-N} > 4m/s^2$  then
18:          Different movements
19:          goto LoMoCA
20:        else
21:           $A_M$  non-normalized
22:           $A_P$  and  $A_M$  not relevant
23:          goto Axis selection
24:   Dynamic limit determination:
25:     if  $|S_M - S_P| > 10$  and  $S_M > 4$  then
26:        $DL_M$  determination
27:        $DL \leftarrow$  greater  $\{DL_M, DL_P\}$ 
28:     else
29:       goto LoMoCA
30:   DTW:
31:     DF calculation through DTW
32:     if  $DF < DL$  then
33:       Possible axis match
34:     else
35:       goto LoMoCA
36:     if Last axis = false then
37:       goto Axis selection
38:     if  $DF$  each axis  $< DL$  each axis then
39:       Possible pattern match
40:     if Last pattern = false then
41:       goto LoMoCA
42:   Similarity analysis:
43:     if Several possible matches then
44:        $DF_T \leftarrow \frac{\sum DF_{RA}}{N_{RA}}$ 
45:       Minimum  $DF_T$  selection
46:     Movement recognized

```

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} DL_M = S_M \cdot 38 + 30, & \{S_M, DL_M\} \in \mathbb{N} \\ DL_P = S_P \cdot 38 + 30, & \{S_P, DL_P\} \in \mathbb{N} \\ DL = \max\{DL_M, DL_P\} & \\ 182 \leq DL \leq 600, & \text{when } 4 \leq \{S_M, S_P\} \leq 15 \\ DL = 600, & \text{when } S_M > 15 \text{ or } S_P > 15 \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

The final dynamic limit corresponds to the maximum value obtained between the calculation referring to the pattern and the one referring to the movement. The limit is set at 600 (the established maximum limit) when the number of samples exceeds 15, i.e. when the movements last more than 1.5 seconds. This upper limit was determined during the experimentation, since the filtering performed at this stage would be negatively affected if increased further, producing an inaccurate classification.

Subsequently, the DTW algorithm is used to make a comparison of the two motion sequences in a tighter way, minimizing the errors caused by the temporary mismatch. If the differential factors obtained for each relevant axis are below the dynamic limit calculated previously, the system continues to compare the movement performed with the rest of the patterns, following the same procedure. Finally, when there are many potential matches, a similarity analysis is conducted. The pattern with the lowest average of differential factors, considering only the relevant axes, is selected and the movement is recognized.

3.4. System Properties

A correct evaluation of the properties of the system requires observing from different approaches. The search of solutions to problems of very diverse fields makes it necessary to classify their properties based on the variables that need to be observed into the following points:

- *LoMoCA* was developed focusing on requirements such as real-time, scalability and energy consumption optimization. In addition, lightweight and low-power devices have been used to validate our approach. Thus, by verifying that the requirements are met by these devices, we highlight the feasibility of the proposal for more performance-demanding scenarios, where only more powerful devices would be needed.
- By sending only data from relevant movements, *OperaBLE* is able to save energy. A pre-filter that can distinguish between vibrations and intentional

movements has been fitted in this device. The rest of the time the device remains in a deep sleep mode, waking up when there is an interruption caused by the accelerometer.

- Real-time, flexibility and scalability requirements are some of the cornerstones for Industry 4.0. Through precise management and a good selection of technologies, the system is highly adaptable. It is versatile enough to set up many different configurations and to work in real time to satisfy the demands of industrial processes.
- High scalability is achieved, with communications and processing being key factors in distinguishing information from wearables when the SBC controls many devices from different workers. Management becomes even more complex when working with asynchronous execution instructions. For this reason, the management performed in the processing algorithm is really meticulous to preserve the independence of the data.
- Process adaptability is guaranteed as the configuration of worker-robots is adapted to the needs of the type of industry and the task to be performed at any given time. This is because the system allows (1) the handling of many robots by the same worker at the same time, thus achieving a mass production, and also (2) the handling of robots by different workers to perform customization tasks and make the process more flexible when necessary.
- The human approach provides natural robot control, reducing the learning time required by operators by offering an easy-to-use system. Furthermore, compared to machine vision systems, it preserves the privacy of workers, achieving a greater user confidence in this type of technology.

4. Experimentation

The proposed gesture control system has many aspects that must be adequately validated through testing. In order to evaluate our proposal, we have used a fixed robot that possesses six joints, ending in a gripper to pick up and move objects. A workspace consisting of a 3×3 matrix, in which a low-cost self-assembled robot has been inserted, has been defined (see Figure 3). The robotic arm performs six different movements: forward, backward, left, right, catch, and release. In addition, nine possible positions of the robotic arm have been established within the matrix (from P11 to P33).

Figure 3. Experimental setup.

The experimentation conducted is divided into two main parts. Firstly, there is a technical approach, where aspects related to the system's performance are studied. Then, a human-centered approach is intended to assess whether the potential users perceive this control system as natural and which is the level of acceptance of the technology for possible use in industrial environments.

4.1. Technical Approach

In this section, we explain the procedure and the configuration followed to develop the experiments related to the technical part. First, it is important to describe in detail the data set and the procedure followed to perform the experiments. Regarding the patterns stored in the processing board, they were added before the beginning of the experiments. This decision was taken to preserve the same conditions during all the tests. For this reason, as well, each pattern was recorded in isolation by the same person. A single pattern of each movement was used, except in the case of *pick/drop* for which four were saved to cover the different manners of performing this movement. Except for the usability test, the person who recorded the patterns conducted the technical experiments, since the system is designed so that each user stores his/her own patterns. The number of samples of each movement varied from four to eight in the shortest movements (*forward*; *backward*; *left*; *right*) and between eight and fourteen when *pick/drop* was performed.

Figure 4 shows some sequences of an operation example, in which all the resources provided to the sys-

tem have been used to emulate a real situation. There are two pieces (placed in P11 and P13) that must be positioned in other points of the matrix (P33 and P31, respectively). To perform the movement of the pieces, different speed modes were selected according to the task at hand. In this case, the maximum operating speed was chosen to carry the objects. The lowest speed was fixed to pick them up or place them on the required position in order to increase the precision. This example ends with an emergency stop, as shown in Figure 4d, so that the robot immediately returns to its home position. Then, the system enters into an emergency mode where it is necessary to perform a manual reset in order to restore the normal operation.

This experiment was designed to measure the time required for the realization of each of the stages that constitute the system, as well as the total time until launching the corresponding action in the robotic arm. The sequence diagram followed to measure the times at each stage is depicted in Figure 5.

At the top, we show the procedure used to measure control commands and movements, while the method related to the measurement of the emergency state is shown below. Firstly, *ControlaBLE* sends a control command, which is processed and forwarded to the controller board. Then, movement data from *OperABLE* are processed by *LoMoCA* so that a movement command is sent to the controller board. Finally, this board reports the current state of the robot. At the bottom, Figure 5 shows the measurement process followed to calculate the time when the emergency stop is triggered. *ControlaBLE* sends the corresponding command three times to avoid possible transmission failures. The processing device sends a home command to the robot controller, which reports the final status. All test times that are shown in Section 5.1.2 have been measured by sending back a confirmation message (ACK) to the device upon receiving the command and taking half of the final time.

4.2. Human-Centered Approach

The human factor is essential for technological breakthroughs. In the case of industrial environments, where the workers might not accept changes or be prepared to adapt to them, there can be a rejection of technologies that could be useful to improve the performance of industrial processes to be developed. In order to get some first impressions from users about the acceptance and usability of the proposed solution and

Figure 4. Operation with work piece handling through the workspace [42].

Figure 5. Latency test design.

the implemented system, we have used the well-known USE questionnaire [53].

The experiment was designed in several steps, making modifications to obtain more useful information, and adjusting the tasks to be performed by the participants. Firstly, the USE test questions were adjusted to orient them to the proposed gesture control system. Once the questionnaire was completed it was shown to five people who did not know how the system worked. As a result, some ambiguities in the wording of the questions were resolved. Subsequently, three experts in this field were contacted to improve the questionnaire and the experimental method in order to obtain more accurate information. Finally, the structure of the questionnaire consists of questions to collect background information about the users and three blocks of the USE questionnaire: ease of use, ease of learning and satisfaction. Each question is scored from 1 to 5 points, the maximum corresponds to the best score.

The final version of the questionnaire was passed to a total of 15 users, nine of which were experts in the fields related to this work such as human-machine interface, wireless communications and robotics, while the other users were people not related with technol-

ogy. The selection focused on the following aspects, which were considered important in order to obtain valuable information from this test: age, area of knowledge and use of technology.

In relation to age, the users were between 22 and 55 years old, which constitutes a broad sample that allows us to observe possible differences in the perception of the system. Users also answered a question about the use of technology in their daily lives. Most of them used technology on a daily basis (80%). However, 13.3% were occasional users and 6.7% did not use technology. Users without technological skills are of great interest, as it is intended that the system can be used by all kinds of people. In this study, a technological user would be people really trained in the use of computers and smart phones, and an occasional user (not daily) if they use the technology to develop minor works. Finally, we considered a non-technological user to be someone who has difficulties in performing simple tasks with technological devices.

The saved patterns of each movement were not modified to adapt them to each user, since this experiment had the purpose of knowing the level of acceptance, adequacy and satisfaction of this system to the user, not to value the success rate or the execution time, as done in the previous tests. Nonetheless, it would be interesting to address, as a whole, the perception of all factors by users in further research.

The proposed tasks for testing the operation of the control system started with an adaptation period where the users practiced to get used to the manner of performing the movements (adjusted to the patterns previously recorded). The workspace used to perform this test is the one shown in Figure 3. After a few minutes, the users had to move the robot from position P32 to P11 and back again to P32. Finally, a more complex task had to be done. The participants had to pick up an

object placed in P21, carry it through the matrix from P21 to P23, drop it, and activate the emergency state.

5. Results

This section is divided into two parts, according to the character of the experiments. The first, of a technical nature, is intended to analyze accuracy and latency data. The second aims to address the possible problems of this system from a human point of view.

A few details should be clarified beforehand, since there are some aspects considered throughout all the experiments. First, we were interested in determining the influence of the speed of movement execution. Some movements were obtained with twice the number of samples than other experiments of the same type. However, this did not imply a change in performance. This means that the system is not dependent on the speed of execution, which provides flexibility and accuracy. Second, another important aspect considered was the user's position both during the accuracy and usability experiments. The results obtained showed that there were no significant differences between users who performed the test sitting or standing, which is an advantage over other systems that require a fixed position for a proper operation.

5.1. Results of the Technical Tests

In our proposal, two main experiments were conducted in the technical block in order to obtain the success rate of the system and the total time invested in the whole control process. We consider that these aspects are essential to assess the technical adequacy of our system to industrial environments. In addition to these tests, a third experiment was carried out in which it was possible to obtain information related to the performance of three more tasks of higher complexity.

5.1.1. Accuracy

The first study (test) focused on the accuracy of the system in movement recognition, i.e. the success rate of our *LoMoCA* recognition algorithm. The movements were performed following random sequences in order to obtain reliable results. Each movement was repeated 100 times to obtain the results shown in Table 4.

As can be observed, *OperaBLE* movements were above 95% success in all cases. The worst was the *forward* movement, which could be due to the different

possibilities to perform this movement. However, this fact is not worrying since it is really close to the success rate of the other movements.

Regarding *ControlaBLE*, the accuracy is between 90% and 100%. The lowest values are due to the potential ambiguity of *Medium* and *High*, which are positions that can be performed with different angles, thus reducing the movement recognition. The total average success obtained for *OperaBLE* is 97% while *ControlaBLE* reaches 96.40%, which is outstanding in both cases.

A much more demanding experiment, called sequence recognition, was carried out to test the behavior of the system by performing three different tasks of growing difficulty. In this case, the movements explained previously were linked one with each other to complete the proposed actions. The first task consisted in picking up an object in P32 and moving it to P23 (see Figure 3). This involved four movements which were *pick, right, forward* and *drop*. The second was to move an object from P23 to P32 starting with the robot at P32 position. This was a six-movement task composed of *right, forward, pick, left, backward, drop*. The third and most challenging task combined the handling of two objects. This process started by picking a part in position P21 and moving it to P32, then another part in P22 was placed in the position of the previous object. This task was carried out using 10 movements listed as follows in order of execution: *forward, left, pick, right, backward, drop, forward, pick, left, drop*. A video demonstration of this task is included as supplementary material.

Each task was performed 50 times, half of the time with the user standing and half sitting, for a total of 1000 movements. When a single movement was missed, the entire action was considered as not recognized. The results obtained showed an accuracy of 96% for the first task and 92% for the rest. As expected, the greater the number of movements that were involved in a task, the greater the probability that one of them would not be recognized. However, this did not represent a significant problem, since the system is prepared to allow the user to correct this type of failure easily. The total failures during the experiment considering the kinds of movements were the following: 2 *forward*, 1 *backward*, 2 *left*, 4 *right*, 1 *pick/drop*.

There was only one noticeable difference between performing the movement when standing or sitting. The failures in the execution of the *right* movement increased in the case of sitting, since all missed *right* movements occurred in this pose. The reason is that

Table 4
Accuracy test results (success rate).

	<i>OperaBLE</i>					<i>ControlaBLE</i>				
	Forward	Backward	Left	Right	Pick/Drop	Inactive	Low	Medium	High	Emergency
Failures	5	4	3	3	0	0	3	10	5	0
Success rate	95%	96%	97%	97%	100%	100%	97%	90%	95%	100%

when sitting, the naturalness in performing this movement is reduced.

5.1.2. Latency

Regarding latency, Table 5 shows a compendium of average response times (in milliseconds). The time at each stage of the system has been calculated after performing each movement 50 times. The procedure followed to measure these intervals consists in sending back an ACK to the transmitting device after completing each stage, computing half of the time obtained, as explained before.

The first column (*Wearables - Processing*) shows the time elapsed between sending the data via BLE and receiving them by the processing device. In all the cases, the time is quite similar; around 21 ms. Once the processing device has received all the data, different procedures are applied depending on the data source. The most common value is 21.50 ms and the standard deviation shows that the data are similar to each other.

The data obtained from *OperaBLE* are processed by *LoMoCA* in order to identify the movement performed. The average time obtained is 31.5 ms, where a maximum value of 65 ms and a minimum of 18 ms have been obtained considering all the tests. The most frequent value in this case is 20 ms. The dispersion of the data is low, with a standard deviation of 8, since 90% of the results are between 18 and 42 ms.

The processing time of the command received from *ControlaBLE* is different. The results show an average of 1.14 ms for the preparation of the corresponding command that will be sent later to the robot control device. The maximum time obtained during the tests is 8 ms, while the minimum is negligible.

The transmission of information between the processing board and controller via MQTT represents the last stage. The results show similar values in the transmission duration for both wearables, obtaining an average of 7.64 ms for *OperaBLE* and 5.34 ms for *ControlaBLE*. Two sporadic values have been found, reaching 27.5 and 29.5 ms in each case. However, 85% and 95% values are below 10 ms.

The values related to the robot movement have been excluded from this evaluation, as the robot used is not

industrial and cannot withstand high working speeds. Thus, the average final time obtained since a movement is made until it starts in the robot is 60.38 ms, while the control commands take an average time of 27.74 ms. In view of the results obtained and according to studies related to the response time requirements, the proposed system is considered suitable for industrial environments in real-time, as it stands below 100 ms [49].

5.1.3. Comparison With Other Approaches

This section is intended to provide a comprehensive comparison with other approaches. Although a fair comparison is only possible with studies using IMUs and focusing on arm movement recognition, an extension to computer vision systems has been considered convenient. In this regard, despite not being aimed at covering the same requirements, the results obtained can be compared in a general context.

To this end, recent literature was studied to compare methods, algorithms, and systems proposed for gesture recognition (see Table 6). Significant features were selected to provide a meaningful comparison. In order to properly evaluate our low frequency sampling algorithm, it was considered advisable to generate our own data set. Short gestures were selected to assess the accuracy with a reduced number of samples.

Contribution type distinguished between works that were assessed with data sets generated by other researchers or with their own experimental validation. It also includes if the approach was focused on a real application. *Area* showed whether a paper was focused on topics related to Industry 4.0, IoT and HRI, which are the topics of the present paper. The types of sensors used for gesture recognition are also considered, which may IMU as in our case, RGB or depth cameras.

There were further aspects considered in the comparison. The accuracy referred to percentage of gestures recognized. As explained in Section 2, industrial environments consider tasks to be real-time when the latency is less than 100 ms. Four categories were defined to classify power consumption of the processing device: low for less than 10 W, medium when between 10 W and 100 W, high when above 100 W, and very

Table 5
Latency time test results (ms).

		Wearables - Processing			Processing			Processing - Controller			Total	
		\bar{x}	mode	s	\bar{x}	mode	s	\bar{x}	mode	s	\bar{x}	$\bar{\bar{x}}$
<i>OperaBLE</i>	Forward	21.14			31.44			7.67			60.25	
	Backward	21.33			32.82			7.75			61.90	
	Left	21.27	21.50	0.79	29.50	20.00	8.91	7.15	6.50	3.33	57.92	60.38
	Right	21.22			30.04			6.63			57.89	
	Pick/Drop	21.20			33.72			9.02			63.94	
<i>ControlaBLE</i>	Low	21.38			1.26			5.67			28.31	
	Medium	21.36	21.50	0.80	1.10	1.00	1.14	5.07	4.50	2.80	27.53	27.74
	High	21.20			1.12			5.20			27.52	
	Emergency	21.12			1.08			5.40			27.60	

Table 6
Comparison with other proposals.

Work	Contribution type			Area			Type of sensors			Features					
	Predefined data sets	Experimental validation	Real application	Industry 4.0	IoT	HRI	IMU	RGB camera	Depth camera	Accuracy	Real time	Processing time (ms)	Power consumption	Adaptability	Operating speed
[16]	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	✓	86.60%-93.66%	✓ ⁽¹⁾	48-62	High ⁽²⁾	Low	-
[17]	x	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	✓	98.90%	x	200-250	High	Low	Low
[38]	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	82.07%	x	NDA	High	Low	-
[28]	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	84.52%-98.60%	x	1725-35525	High ⁽²⁾	Low	-
[39]	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	84.12%-98.75%	x	NDA	High ⁽²⁾	Low	-
[37]	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	84.20%-98.90%	x	NDA	High	Low	-
[40]	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	90.33%-98.50%	✓	38	Very High	Low	-
[30]	x	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	✓	93.00%-96.00%	x	158	High ⁽²⁾	High	High
[33]	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	96.66%	x	NDA	High ⁽²⁾	Low	Low
[34]	x	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x	✓	NDA	x	NDA	High ⁽²⁾	High	Low
[32]	x	✓	✓	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	NDA	x	380	High ⁽²⁾	High	Low
[41]	✓	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	79.10%	x	NDA	High ⁽²⁾	Low	-
[6]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	98.00%	x	1000	High ⁽²⁾	Low	Low
[14]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	94.20%	x	NDA	High ⁽²⁾	Low	Low
Ours	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	97.00%	✓	32	Low	High	High⁽³⁾

(1) No standard deviation provided. Real time is not guaranteed; (2) No information provided. Estimation extracted from the hardware requirements for the technology used;

(3) Regarding the type of robot the system is intended for.

high when over 1000 W. Adaptability was evaluated in terms of the ability to adapt to changing requirements adding new movements. Finally, the operating speed is related to the type of robot it is intended for. Low when the robot is designed to share the workspace with the operator and high for traditional industrial robots. The NDA term stands for no data available.

The selection of papers was intended to cover a wide range of sensors, aiming at the most recent and advanced articles in terms of accuracy and real time. The comparison started with systems that used RGB cameras, although most also used depth ones, since the Microsoft Kinect device includes this type of sensor. The majority of them used predefined data sets to assess the recognition accuracy of their algorithms. As shown in Table 6, they reached high accuracy rates [37,39,28]. However, they were not capable of providing real-time operation, which is a key feature in industrial applications. Usually this kind of systems uses complex arti-

ficial intelligence methods in order to improve the accuracy but this impacts on processing time.

In some cases, real-time recognition of gestures was achieved, although the hardware requirements were really demanding and the methods did not permit a flexible management of the gestures [16,40]. However, when only the average processing time was provided [16], without standard deviation, the total time was extremely close to the limit, probably not complying with the real-time restriction in some cases. Other related studies using RGB and depth cameras were aimed at real applications, therefore they developed their own data set [38,17,30]. These systems did not achieve real time, the hardware elements were considerably more powerful and the adaptability was lower than that of our proposal. Moreover, compared to our system, only one proposal obtained a better accuracy [17].

Some commercial devices are widely employed to recognize movements. An example is the *Leap Motion Controller*, which is composed of several IR emitters and cameras (depth cameras). Some papers using this device were included in the comparative table [33]. Despite the high accuracy obtained, the method to include new gestures is not flexible enough to permit rapid changes. On the contrary, other systems are flexible, as they provide continuous monitoring of the gestures to reproduce them on the robotic arm [32,34]. Apart from the lack of accuracy values, the requirement of real-time is not satisfied. Moreover, this gesture recognition device, according to the requirements specified by the device manufacturer, needs processing equipment whose power consumption is up to 50 times higher than the one used in our work.

Finally, another option is to implement systems with IMU as recognition method. A mixed system that consists of RGB and depth cameras and an IMU to improve gesture recognition has been proposed [41]. In other articles, the main sensors used to obtain movement data in the system are IMUs [6,14]. In these cases, in spite of the high accuracy demonstrated by the experimental validation aimed at a real application in Industry 4.0, the real-time requirement is not fulfilled and both systems need prior training, which does not provide the desired adaptability.

5.2. Results of the Human-Centered Tests

This section shows the results gathered in a questionnaire related to the acceptance and usability of the system by real users. It is divided into three main blocks, following the structure of the questionnaire used, where the results of the encompassed questions are commented.

An analysis has been carried out to select the 5's responses of the 19 questions of the questionnaire, since they are the ones that provide the most valuable information to determine if they consider the system to be simple to use, intuitive and suitable for the industry. Figure 6 shows the users' answers to these questions, rated from 1 to 5, with the higher the better in all cases.

Ease of use. The aim of the questions in this block is to find out how the users perceive the naturalness and simplicity of use of the proposed gesture control. Question *Q1*, in Figure 6, corresponds to "The control system is easy to use", where we can observe that 13 users scored 4 or 5 points and two opted for 3 points.

According to these answers, it seems that the control system is easy to use for different types of people.

Figure 6. Most representative responses to the questionnaire.

The most important aspect in this case is that, as was observed during the experiment, the ease of use does not depend on the age of the people. This is a really significant point, as one of the key elements that this type of control is intended to address is the technological gap between generations. Neither does the type of studies of the user influence his/her management.

Nevertheless, question *Q2* shows some answers with a decreased score. This question refers to the level of effort that the users consider they had to make during the test. The explanation to this fact was obtained after reading the comments from the users, since it was known that one of the most challenging tasks for them was the coordination of both arms during the experiment. The users considered the *OperaBLE* movements natural and simple to learn and remember. However, the control movements performed with *ControlaBLE* were not felt as intuitive as the previous ones and much less when they had to be performed in conjunction with the other arm. This is an interesting point to bear in mind in later revisions to enhance the system.

Despite the diversity of opinions regarding the effort required, 14 users out of 15 thought that this control system could be useful to both occasional and regular users. In addition, an important comment was that the users did not need written instructions to control the robot, as they understood the instructions easily and remembered them without any problem. This is another example of the intuitiveness of this gesture control. The ease of use when performing the robot's movements is appreciable.

Ease of learning. The purpose of this block of questions is to evaluate the ease of learning of the gesture control system. Question *Q3* is related to the learning curve associated with the system. In this case, the participants answered the question "It is easy to learn to

use it". As can be seen, the users considered that they learned to use it in an easy manner.

This block of questions also reveals that 90% of the users affirmed that they learned to use the control system quickly. However, one of the users was left-handed and, due to the decision to share the original motion patterns in all users' tests, this user had more difficulties getting used to performing the movements as they were recorded.

Satisfaction. The users rated questions about their overall satisfaction with this HRI system. Figure 6 also shows the responses to the question of whether they considered this control system advisable for workers in the industry, which is shown under question *Q4*. As can be appreciated, all the users considered that this gesture control is appropriate for the workers, since five of them scored this question with four points and ten with the highest qualification. Moreover, the users rated their compliance with the statement "It is pleasant to use this gesture control system" in question *Q5*, where most participants agreed with this claim, although the score dropped due to the coordination problems mentioned previously. Therefore, they believed that it is a gesture control system that poses an alternative to the future of HRI in Industry 4.0, although some possible improvements have been appreciated in this initial phase that could enhance the user-friendliness of this control system.

In view of the results, we affirm that the use of motion sensors such as accelerometers and gyroscopes [10], the recognition achieved by our *LoMoCA* algorithm, the management of communications, and the implementation of the system seem adequate for the very diverse users who tested this HRI system [14] oriented to the Industry 4.0.

6. Conclusions

This article has presented a HRI system consisting of two wearables, called *ControlaBLE* and *OperaBLE*, a processing device, a control device, and a robotic arm used to perform tests of the entire system. The process starts with the capture of motion and control data by the two IoT wristbands. The data are sent via BLE to the processing device, where our own low-sampling-rate motion recognition algorithm, called *LoMoCA*, has been implemented. As evidenced, this algorithm enables a reduction in the amount of data to be processed in order to recognize each move-

ment. This means that, with up to 10 times less information than other related approaches, excellent results in movement recognition are achieved. As a result, it offers great advantages, since it allows the use of low-power, lightweight, and cost-effective devices, as well as a reduction in processing time, making it possible to perform operations in real-time.

Remote control of the robotic arm is achieved by means of the MQTT protocol. Communication management, accurate implementation and excellent motion recognition performance give the system different capabilities of great importance to Industry 4.0. The proposal's capabilities are: scalability, due to its ability to process multiple devices at the same time, which increases the production rate; flexibility, as workers can control several robots simultaneously or perform different tasks with each of them when necessary, achieving a customized production plant adapted to the requirements at every moment; real-time, since the time needed to send the data, process the movement and activate the corresponding control command remotely is less than 100 ms. This is an indispensable requirement in industrial environments that has been possible by reducing the number of samples to process, even using low-cost and low-power devices.

The proposed gesture control system has been tested on technical aspects such as accuracy in movement recognition and response time. A human-centered study has also been conducted to analyze if the users will perceive this gesture control as intuitive and if they consider that this technology could be used by workers in the industry. The impressions of the users have been gathered by means of a questionnaire completed after performing a robot control experiment. Technological advances cannot be built leaving society aside. For this reason, we believe that the accomplishment of this type of experiments is worthwhile to assure the acceptance of the advances that can be positive for society. Furthermore, experiments with real users have led to positive improvements that will help the future success in the deployment of the system.

As future work, our objective is to test the system in real environments, evaluating other aspects related to industrial plants. In this study we wanted to use our own data set to push the system to the limit with extremely short movements. In this sense, the experiments were performed in the worst case for our low-sampling frequency movement recognition algorithm. However, in future research it would be interesting to introduce new data sets to obtain results of other types of movements and test our proposal with a larger num-

ber of users, including different ways of interaction and a proper comparison with them. Furthermore, the introduction of a continuous improvement of learning and merging with other systems is a challenge that we will face in future studies.

To conclude, the developed gesture control system provides a natural, straightforward and flexible manner of controlling robots. It has been tested from a technical perspective and also with real users achieving excellent results. Thus, thanks to the features achieved, this HRI system meets key requirements of Industry 4.0 and can be a great starting point for creating adaptable and advanced industrial systems in which to obtain the maximum benefit from human-robot collaboration for all stakeholders.

Acknowledgments

This work was partially supported by Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, Agencia Estatal de Investigación (AEI) / European Regional Development Fund (FEDER, UE) under PID2019-106084RB-I00, RTI2018-098156-B-C52 and DPI2016-80894-R projects, and by VALU3S EU project (H2020-ECSEL grant agreement no 876852). Luis Roda-Sanchez is pursuing his Industrial PhD under DIN2018-010177 grant from Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación. José Luis de la Vara holds a “Ramon y Cajal” fellowship (RYC-2017-22836) from Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación. Celia Garrido-Hidalgo holds 2019-PREDUCLM-10703 fellowship from FEDER, UE at Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha.

References

- [1] Famaey, J. et al.: Flexible multimodal sub-gigahertz communication for heterogeneous Internet of Things applications. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, **56**(7), 146–153 (2018)
- [2] Sabri, L., Bouznad, S., Rama Fiorini, S., Chibani, A., Prestes, E., Amirat, Y.: An integrated semantic framework for designing context-aware Internet of Robotic Things systems. *Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering*, **25**(2), 137–156 (2018)
- [3] Garrido-Hidalgo, C., Olivares, T., Ramirez, F.J., Roda-Sanchez, L.: An end-to-end Internet of Things solution for reverse supply chain management in Industry 4.0. *Computers in Industry*, **112**, 103127–103140 (2019)
- [4] Boyes, H., Hallaq, B., Cunningham, J., Watson, T.: The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT): An analysis framework. *Computers in Industry*, **101**, 1–12 (2018)
- [5] Lei, Q., Zhang, H., Yang, Y., He, Y., Bai, Y., Liu, S.: An investigation of applications of hand gestures recognition in industrial robots. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Robotic*, **8**(5) (2019).
- [6] Neto, P., Simão, M., Mendes, N., Safeea, M.: Gesture-based human-robot interaction for human assistance in manufacturing. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, **101**, 1–4 (2019).
- [7] Rosen, E., Whitney, D., Phillips, E., Chien, G., Tompkin, J., Konidaris, G., Tellex, S.: Communicating and controlling robot arm motion intent through mixed-reality head-mounted displays. *International Journal of Robotics Research*, **38**(12–13), 1513–1526 (2019).
- [8] Pellegri-nelli, S., Pedrocchi, N.: Estimation of robot execution time for close proximity human-robot collaboration. *Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering*, **25**(1), 81–96 (2018)
- [9] Peruzzini, M., Grandi, F., Pellicciari, M.: Benchmarking of tools for user experience analysis in Industry 4.0. *Procedia Manufacturing*, **11**, 806–813 (2017)
- [10] Neto, P., Pires, J.N., Moreira, A.P.: Accelerometer-based control of an industrial robotic arm. RO-MAN 2009 - The 18th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication, **11**, 1192–1197 (2009)
- [11] Prakash, P., Dhanasekaran, C., Surya, K., Varunni Pius, K., Vishal, A.S., Vignesh Kumar, S.: Gesture controlled dual six axis robotic arms with rover using MPU. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, (21), 547–556 (2020)
- [12] Dajun, Z., Minghui, S., Fei, C., Chih-Min, L., Longzhi, Y., Changjing, S., Changle, Z.: Use of human gestures for controlling a mobile robot via adaptive CMAC network and fuzzy logic controller. *Neurocomputing*, **282**, 218–231 (2018)
- [13] Li, Y., Yang, N., Li, L., Liu, L., Yang, Y.: Finger gesture recognition using a smartwatch with integrated motion sensors. *Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering*, **16**(2), 123–129 (2018)
- [14] Mendes, N., Ferrer, J., Vitorino, J., Safeea, M., Neto, P.: Human behavior and hand gesture classification for smart human-robot interaction. *Procedia Manufacturing*, **11**, 91–98 (2017)
- [15] Wu, H., Yang, L., Fu, S., Zhang, X.: Beyond remote control: Exploring natural gesture inputs for smart TV systems. *Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering*, **11**(4), 335–354 (2019)
- [16] Dong, J., Xia, Z., Yan, W., Zhao, Q.: Dynamic gesture recognition by directional pulse coupled neural networks for human-robot interaction in real time. *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, **63** (2019)
- [17] Mazhar, O., Navarro, B., Ramdani, S., Passama, R., Cherubini, A.: A real-time human-robot interaction framework with robust background invariant hand gesture detection. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, **60**, 34–48 (2019)
- [18] Gao, Q., Liu, J., Ju, Z., Zhang, X.: Dual-hand detection for human-robot interaction by a parallel network based on hand detection and body pose estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, **66**(12), 9663–9672 (2019)
- [19] Du, G., Zhang, P.: A markerless human-robot interface using particle filter and Kalman filter for dual robots. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, **62**(4), 2257–2264 (2015)
- [20] Hongyang, Z., Shuangquan, W., Gang, Z., Daqing, Z.: Ultigesture: A wristband-based platform for continuous gesture control in healthcare. *Smart Health*, **11**, 45–65 (2018)
- [21] Almagro, M., Fresno, V., de la Paz, F.: Speech gestural interpretation by applying word representations in robotics. *Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering* **26**(1), 97–109 (2019)
- [22] Daw-Tung, L., De-Cheng, P.: Integrating a mixed-feature model and multiclass support vector machine for facial expression recognition. *Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering* **16**(1), 61–74 (2009)

- [23] Roda-Sanchez, L., Garrido-Hidalgo, C., Hortelano, D., Olivares, T., Ruiz, M.C.: OperaBLE: An IoT-based wearable to improve efficiency and smart worker care services in Industry 4.0. *Journal of Sensors*, **2018**, 6272793 (2018)
- [24] Garrido-Hidalgo, C., Hortelano, D., Roda-Sanchez, L., Olivares, T., Ruiz, M.C., López, V.: IoT heterogeneous mesh network deployment for human-in-the-loop challenges towards a social and sustainable Industry 4.0. *IEEE Access*, **6**, 28417–28437 (2018)
- [25] Martínez-Gomez, J., Fernández-Caballero, A., García-Varea, I., Rodríguez, L., Romero-Gonzalez, C.: A taxonomy of vision systems for ground mobile robots. *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems*, **11**, 111 (2014)
- [26] Gascueña, J.M., Fernández-Caballero, A.: Agent-oriented modeling and development of a person-following mobile robot. *Expert Systems with Applications*, **38**(4), 4280–4290 (2011)
- [27] Diez-Olivan, A., Del Ser, J., Galar, D., Sierra, B.: Data fusion and machine learning for industrial prognosis: Trends and perspectives towards Industry 4.0. *Information Fusion*, **50**, 92–111 (2019)
- [28] Kiruba, K., Shiloah, E. D., Sunil, R. R. C.: Hexagonal volume local binary pattern (H-VLBP) with deep stacked autoencoder for Human Action Recognition. *Cognitive Systems Research*, **58**, 71–93 (2019)
- [29] Mehta, D., Rhodin, H., Casas, D., Fua, P., Sotnychenko, O., Xu, W., Theobalt, C.: Monocular 3D human pose estimation in the wild using improved CNN supervision. In 2017 International Conference on 3D Vision, 506–516 (2017)
- [30] Tsarouchi, P., Athanasatos, A., Makris, S., Chatzigeorgiou, X., Chryssoulouris, G.: High level robot programming using body and hand gestures. *Procedia CIRP*, **55**, 1–5 (2016)
- [31] Mueller, F., Davis, M., Bernard, F., Sotnychenko, O., Verschoor, M., Otaduy, M.A., Casas, D., Theobalt, C.: Real-time pose and shape reconstruction of two interacting hands with a single depth camera. *ACM Transactions on Graphics*, **38**(4) (2019)
- [32] Devine, S., Rafferty, K., Ferguson, S.: Real time robotic arm control using hand gestures with multiple end effectors. In UKACC International Conference on Control (2016)
- [33] Erdoğan, K., Durdu, A., Yılmaz, N.: Intention recognition using leap motion controller and Artificial Neural Networks. In International Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies, 689–693 (2016)
- [34] Kruusamäe, K., Pryor, M.: High-precision telerobot with human-centered variable perspective and scalable gestural interface. In 9th International Conference on Human System Interactions, 190–196 (2016)
- [35] Sokolova M.V., Serrano-Cuerda J., Castillo J.C. and Fernández-Caballero A.: A fuzzy model for human fall detection in infrared video. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, **24**(2), 215–228 (2013)
- [36] Bachmann, D., Weichert, F., Rinkenauer, G.: Review of three-dimensional human-computer interaction with focus on the Leap Motion controller. *Sensors*, **18**, 2194 (2018)
- [37] Naveenkumar, M., Domic, S.: Deep ensemble network using distance maps and body part features for skeleton based action recognition. *Pattern Recognition*, **100**, 107125 (2020)
- [38] Xu, S., Liang, L., Ji, C.: Gesture recognition for human-machine interaction in table tennis video based on deep semantic understanding. *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, **81**, 115688 (2020)
- [39] Arivazhagan, S., Shebiah, R. N., Harini, R., Swetha, S.: Human action recognition from RGB-D data using complete local binary pattern. *Cognitive Systems Research*, **58**, 94–104 (2019)
- [40] Huynh-The, T., Hua, C.-H., Ngo, T.-T., Kim, D.-S.: Image representation of pose-transition feature for 3D skeleton-based action recognition. *Information Sciences*, **513**, 112–126 (2019)
- [41] Chen, C., Jafari, R., Kehtarnavaz, N.: UTD-MHAD: A multi-modal dataset for human action recognition utilizing a depth camera and a wearable inertial sensor. In International Conference on Image Processing, 168–172 (2015)
- [42] Roda-Sanchez L., Olivares T., Garrido-Hidalgo C., Fernández-Caballero A.: Gesture control wearables for human-machine interaction in Industry 4.0. In: Ferrández Vicente J., Álvarez-Sánchez J., de la Paz López F., Toledo Moreo J., Adeli H. (eds). *From Bioinspired Systems and Biomedical Applications to Machine Learning*, 99–108 (2019)
- [43] Hortelano, D., Olivares, T., Ruiz, M.C., Garrido-Hidalgo, C., López, V.: From sensor networks to Internet of Things. *Bluetooth Low Energy, a standard for this evolution*. *Sensors*, **17**(2), 372 (2017)
- [44] Gascueña, J.M., Navarro, E., Fernández-Sotos, P., Fernández-Caballero, A., Pavón, J.: IDK and ICARO to develop multi-agent systems in support of Ambient Intelligence. *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, **28**(1), 3–15 (2015)
- [45] Rivas-Casado, A., Martínez-Tomás, R., Fernández-Caballero, A.: Multi agent system for knowledge based event recognition and composition. *Expert Systems*, **28**(5), 488–501 (2011)
- [46] Alavi, S., Arsenault, D., Whitehead, A.: Quaternion-based gesture recognition using wireless wearable motion capture sensors. *Sensors*, **16**, 605 (2016)
- [47] Georgi, M., Amma, C., Schultz, T.: Recognizing hand and finger gestures with IMU based motion and EMG based muscle activity sensing. In International Joint Conference on Biomedical Engineering Systems and Technologies, **4**, 99–108 (2015)
- [48] Rondón, R., Gidlund, M., Landernäs, K.: Evaluating Bluetooth low energy suitability for time-critical industrial IoT applications. *International Journal of Wireless Information Networks*, **24**, 278–290 (2017).
- [49] PubNub: How Fast is Realtime? Human Perception and Technology. PubNub Realtime Applications. Last accessed 24 Jan 2020.
- [50] Felsler, M.: Real-Time Ethernet - Industry prospective. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, **93**, 1118–1129 (2005).
- [51] BQ: 3D Printing BQ, Witbox 2. Last accessed 24 Jan 2020.
- [52] IBM: MQTT vs HTTP by IBM, IBM developer. Last accessed 15 Nov 2018.
- [53] Lund, A.: Measuring Usability with the USE Questionnaire. Usability and User Experience Newsletter of the STC Usability SIG, **8** (2001).